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Research Article

**JUDGE THE PEDIATRIC NURSE'S INFORMATION
RELATED TO CHILDREN WITH ATTENTION DEFICIT
HYPERACTIVITY DISORDERS AT NAJRAN CITY****Dr. Howaida Moawad Ahmed Ali**

Assistant Professor Of Pediatric Nursing, Najran University, Saudi Arabia.

Article Received: February 2020**Accepted:** March 2020**Published:** April 2020**Abstract:**

Background: Many children suffer from attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), which is defined as a persistent pattern of inattention or impulsivity that is formed during growth. **The aim** of this study was to examine the pediatric nurses information and attitude related to children with ADHD. **Research design:** A descriptive research design was utilized in this study. **Setting:** The study was conducted at Maternity and Childhood hospital, Najran University at Saudi Arabia. **Sample:** Purposive sample from all pediatric nurses at previously mentioned setting were used in this study. **The tools:** were used in data collection. **Tool 1:Part one:** Involve socio-demographic characteristics of all study samples. **Part two:** Pediatric Nurses information related to children with ADHD. **Tool 11:** Pediatric nurses attitude related to children with ADHD. **Results:** half of pediatric nurses (53%) were in age group of 20:<30 years and the mean age of them was (25.6 ±1.95 years. 83% of the pediatric nurses had positive attitude towards affective attitude of children with ADHD. There was statistically significant difference between pediatric nurses' socio-demographic characteristics and their total level of information and their attitude related to children with ADHD. **Conclusion:** The study concluded that there was most of the pediatric nurses, information in the present study felt inadequate to handle the responsibility of ADHD children. **Recommendations:** An educational program is needed for pediatric nurses to significantly improved the information and attitudes towards children with ADHD. Suggest greater efforts must be made to provide pediatric nurses training specifically in the identification, symptoms, etiology, prognosis and management of the children with ADHD.

Keyword: Nurses, pediatric, ADHD and information, attitude.**Corresponding author:****Corresponding author:****Dr. Howaida Moawad Ahmed Ali,**

Assistant Professors of Pediatric Nursing,

Najran University, Saudi Arabia.

Dr.howaidamoawad@yahoo.com

hemahmed@nu.edu.sa.

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INTRODUCTION:

Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is a heterogeneous neurodevelopmental disorder with a worldwide prevalence of 5–7 % among children and adolescents (Willcutt., 2012). The causes of ADHD is unknown; but the latest indications maintained the role of genetic, neurobiological and environmental issues (Sagiv, et al., 2013).

The children is known as having ADHD when inattention, impulsivity, and hyperactivity behaviors cause a trouble of successful performance in daily activities. So that children with ADHD are habitually at greater risk of unwell dealing life's, including self-care (e.g., the performance of morning routines), production (e.g., low educational achievement) and freedom (e.g., developmentally unsuitable playing skills). later, ADHD interrupts a children normal life and interrelates with the surrounding environment (McCarthy, et al., 2012) and (Raman, et al., 2013).

The children agonize from attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) shown in extra settings (e.g., at home, school or work) and negatively affects the children social, academic. Primary identification and intervention of these disorders are very important to address issues at early age (Bhasin, et al., 2018).

Significant of the study:

The prevalence of ADHD is 16.4% in Saudi Arabia. Boys are more frequently referred and diagnosed than girls (Jasim and Delpert., 2018).

Pediatric nurses who deliver care to children and their relatives in the hospital, school, and community are central memberships of the teams that offer diagnostic, treatment, and support services. Pediatric nurses deliver care not only to children and youth with ADHD who are hospitalized for other diagnostic reasons such as having a special health care need or disability but also to those in the community site (Betz., 2006).

Pediatric nurses, whether in hospital or community settings, have frequent chances not only to offer direct services to children and youth with ADHD but also to teach children and adolescence themselves, their parents, and community-based colleagues about the continuum of care that these children and youth necessity. These requirements include assessment and diagnosis as well as monitoring the children's reaction to the behavioral controlling program and medication for comorbid signs and early symptoms of at-risk behaviors. It is a concern that children and adolescence with ADHD demonstrate an increased need for services and treatment from medical, and educational

earners. It would seem that children and adolescence with ADHD would benefit from care organization, as do other peoples of children with special health care needs and disabilities (Betz., 2006).

Aim of the study:

-Measure the pediatric nurse's information regarding children with AHDS.

-Examine the association between socio-demographic characteristics of pediatric nurses and their information related to children with AHDS.

Research Questions:

- Are the pediatric nurses having appropriate information regarding children with AHDS?
- Are the pediatric nurses having positive attitude regarding children with AHDS?

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

A-Research Design: A descriptive correlation research design was utilized in this study.

B- Setting:

The study was carried out at department of pediatric in maternity and children's hospital at Saudi Arabia.

C- Sample selection: Convenience Sample was used to collect data pertinent to the study. Data were collected within one month. The total number of the sample was 100 from pediatric nurses working at previous mention setting.

D-Tools: Tool I:

Part 1:- A sociodemographic questionnaire obtained information about the pediatric nurses characteristics such as age, marital status, years of experience, previous training on ADHD and qualifications.

Part 2: The Self-report ADHD questionnaire was used to assess pediatric nurses information of symptoms, diagnosis, treatment, nature, causes, role of nurse and outcome of ADHD. Each item is answered as "yes," "No," or "Unknown". The total information of Attention Deficit Disorders Scale has acceptable internal reliability ($\alpha = 0.89$ for the information scale). The correct answers were summed into information score where higher scores indicate good information of ADHD (range 0–21).

Scoring system: The total scores of information question were 44 degrees those who obtained <60% were considered having the unsatisfactory information, while those who obtained ≥ 60 was considered having satisfactory information.

Tool II: The ADHD Attitude Scale was used to assess pediatric nurses beliefs and attitudes about

ADHD. It has 30-items scored on a 5-point Likert-type scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree). Some items in the scale measured cognitive attitude (e.g. “ADHD is an excuse for children to misbehave”), others measured affective attitude (e.g. “I would feel frustrated having to manage a child with ADHD”), and some items tapped into behavioural component of attitude (e.g. “Children with ADHD should not be taught in the regular school system like ours”). The answers were summed to create an ADHD Attitude Scale where higher scores indicate more negative attitude (range 30–150, $\alpha = 0.87$).

Ethical and legal consideration:

The specific objectives, anticipated benefits and the method of the study were carefully explained to each participant, also ethical consideration of the research were maintained. The researchers emphasized that all member participate in the study is entirely voluntary with oral consent, and their rights were secured; anonymity and confidentiality were assured through coding the data.

Tools validity:

Tools were submitted to a panel of two experts in the field of pediatric nursing to test the content validity. Modifications were carried out according

to the panel judgment on the clarity of sentences and appropriateness of content.

Pilot study:

A pilot study was carried out on 5% of the total sample to check the clarity of items and determine the feasibility of the study and included in the sample.

Procedure:

The researchers explained the purpose of the study to each pediatric nurses to gain their cooperation to share in the study. Interviewing the pediatric nurses took place in the pediatric departments. The questioner sheet took around 30-45 minutes to be filled. The researcher collected data during one day a week from January 2019 to February 2019 in the pediatric department.

Statistical analysis:

Collected data were coded and tabulated using the personal computer. Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 24 was used. Descriptive as well as inferential statistics were used to answer the research question. Statistical significance was considered at $p\text{-value} < 0.05$.

RESULTS:

Table (1): Distribution of pediatric nurses according to their age and nationality (N=100)

Variables		No (%)
Age	20:<30	53
	31:<40	23
	41:<50	19
	51:≤60	5
	$\bar{X} \pm S.D$	27.2 ± 1.16
Nationality	Saudi	65
	Filipino	15
	Indian	10
	Egyptian	5
	Others	5

Table 1: shown that more than half of pediatric nurses (53%) were in age group of 20:<30 years and the mean age of them was (25.6 ±1.95 years). While (65%) were in Saudi nationality.

Figure 1: Distribution of pediatric nurses according to their qualification

Figure 1: Illustrated that the majority of pediatric nurses was bachelor's qualification.

Figure 2: Distribution of pediatric nurses according to their years of experiences

Figure 2: Evidenced that more than half of pediatric nurses were had 1-10 years of experience.

Figure 3: Distribution of pediatric nurses according to marital status

Figure 3: showed that half of pediatric nurses were single

Table 2: The percentage of pediatric nurse's information related to children with ADHD (N=100)

Information	Yes	No	Unknown
1. There are a greater number of boys than girls with ADHD	30%	34%	36%
2. If medication is prescribed, educational interventions are often unnecessary	40%	30%	30%
3. ADHD children are born with biological vulnerabilities toward inattention and poor self-control	60%	20%	20%
4. If a child responds to stimulant medications, for example, Ritalin, then he or she probably has ADHD	45%	23%	32%
5. A child who is not overactive, but fails to pay attention, may have ADHD	30%	35%	35%
6. ADHD is often caused by food additives	20%	45%	35%
7. ADHD can be diagnosed in the doctor's office most of the time	78%	20%	2%
8. Children with ADHD always need a quiet environment to concentrate	70%	10%	20%
9. Approximately 5% of school aged children had ADHD	77%	10%	13%
10. ADHD can be inherited	40%	40%	20%
11. Medication is a cure for ADHD	50%	30%	20%
12. All children with ADHD are overactive	80%	20%	0%
13. There are subtypes of	60%	30%	10%

ADHD			
14. ADHD affects male children only	10%	10%	80%
15. The cause of ADHD is unknown	70%	20%	10%
16. ADHD is the result of poor parenting practices			
17. Children with ADHD cannot sit still long enough to pay attention	55%	15%	35%
18. ADHD is caused by too much sugar in the diet child will be diagnosed with ADHD	60%	30%	10%
19. Children from any walk of life can have ADHD	10%	30%	60%
20. Children with ADHD usually have good peer relations because of their outgoing nature	57%	20%	23%
21. Children with ADHD generally display an inflexible adherence to specific routines or rituals	76%	20%	4%

Table 2: showed that high percent 80% of pediatric nurses agree that all children with ADHD are overactive

Figure 4: Total distribution of pediatric nurses' information regarding children with ADHD

Figure 4: Illustrated that the total level of pediatric nurse's information was more than half of them had average information.

Figure 5: Distribution of total pediatric nursing attitude regarding children with ADHD

Figure 5: illustrated that pediatric nurses 83% had positive attitude towards affective attitude of children with ADHD.

Table 3: The association between pediatric nurse's demographic characteristics and their total of information and attitude towards children with ADHD

Pediatric nurses' socio-demographic	Level of information			Level of attitude		X ²	P
	Good	Average	Poor	Positive	Negative		
Age							
20:<30	13	35	5	23	30	9.32	0.01
31:<40	10	10	13	11	12		
41:<50	10	5	4	10	9		
51:≤60	3	2	2	4	1		
Nationality							
Saudi	15	40	10	54	11	8.12	0.05
Filipino	5	8	2	10	5		
Indian	6	2	2	5	5		
Egyptian	2	2	1	3	2		
Qualification							
Diploma	20	20	20	40	20	6.55	0.05
Bachelors	5	21	14	20	15		
Master	3	1	0	2	1		
PHD	1	1	0	1	1		
Years of experiences							
1-10y	20	35	20	55	20	7.23	0.05
11-20y	10	5	5	12	8		
More than 21 years	3	2	0	3	2		
Marital status							
Married	10	10	18	30	8	4.21	0.01
Single	20	15	15	35	15		
Widowed	3	2	2	5	2		
Separated	3	1	1	3	2		

As clear from table (3) found that, there was statistically significant difference between nurses' socio-demographic characteristics and their total level of information and their attitude related to children with ADHD, where pediatric nurses had good information were age between 20:<30 years. while those had average information were Saudi nationality and Bachelors qualification. While those had poor information were from 1-10 years of experience.

DISCUSSION:

Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) affects nearly 13% of school-age children, primarily male children, making it the most prevalent behavior problem of childhood.

The current study showed that more than half of pediatric nurses (53%) were in age group of 20:<30 years and the mean age was (25.6 ±1.95 years). While (65%) were in Saudi nationality. Also, the majority of pediatric nurses was bachelor's qualification, and had 1-10 years of experience, also, half of the pediatric nurses were single. These study matched with study done by (Young, et al., 2008) who found that the mean age of the subjects were 42.44 (SD=5.74) ranging from 32 to 61. Almost 88% of subjects were married and 63.9% of them received 4 years university education. The mean years of career as a school nurse was 17.60 (SD=5.63) ranging from 0.5 to 35.

The present study found that the total level of pediatric nurse's information was more than half of them had average information. While 83% of the pediatric nurses had positive attitude towards affective attitude of children with ADHD. These results in the same line with study done by (Youssef, et al., 2015) who found that total knowledge scores were low, mean 12.6/26. Attitudes toward children with ADHD were generally positive although most teachers felt children with ADHD should be taught by specialist teachers.

The current study revealed that there was statistically significant difference between nurses' socio-demographic characteristics and their total level of information related children with ADHD. where pediatric nurses had good information were age between 20:<30 years. while those had average information were Saudi nationality and Bachelors qualification. While those had poor information were from 1-10 years of experience. These results are similar to those of (Shehata, et al., 2016) who reported that some demographic variables as ages, educational qualifications, and years of teaching experience had a significant Positive correlation with post assessment teachers' knowledge. In addition the study done by (Dodangi, et al., 2017) who found that very low knowledge and even incorrect beliefs. The parent's knowledge significantly correlated with their educational level (p=0.01).

CONCLUSION:

The study concluded that there was most of the pediatric nurses, information in the present study felt inadequate to handle the responsibility of ADHD children.

Recommendations:

-An educational program is needed for pediatric nurses to significantly improved the information and attitudes towards children with ADHD.

- Suggest greater efforts must be made to provide pediatric nurses training specifically in the identification, symptoms, etiology, prognosis and management of the children with ADHD.

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